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Prospects for Improving International Financial Reporting Standards in Uzbekistan

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***Abstract:** The purpose of this article is to review the process of reforming accounting and reporting in Uzbekistan in accordance with IFRS.*

***Key words:** IAS, IFRS, accounting, transition, risk.*

The development of market relations in our country, the establishment of long-term trade relations, the establishment of organizations with foreign investment and the issuance of securities on the international market require foreign partners to overcome difficulties in understanding the information contained in the financial statements of organizations.

In the business and professional world, the financial reporting system described by International Financial Reporting Standards (IFRS) is recognized as the most convenient way to a market economy. This provides the market with useful financial information for a wide range of interested users, enabling new, effective management of the company, which is why IFRS is an important component of quality corporate governance. International Financial Reporting Standards (IFRSs) are a set of rules governing the recognition, evaluation and disclosure of financial transactions for the preparation of financial statements of companies around the world. Financial reporting standards provide a comparison of accounting documents between companies globally, as well as the transparency and convenience of reporting information for external users.

International accounting standards allow not only to reduce the cost of companies to prepare reports (especially in the context of strengthening the financial statements of enterprises operating in different countries), but also to reduce the cost of raising capital. It is known that the market price of capital is determined by two main factors: prospective profit and risk. Risk is important for some companies themselves, but the lack of information, lack of accurate information about the return on investment is one of the main shortcomings. One of the reasons for the lack of information is the lack of standardized financial reporting, which, while maintaining capital, increases it. This is because investors prefer to reduce the risk of data disclosure, even if they earn a little less.

Summarizing the advantages of IFRS, we can say that for financial analysts and investors it is cheaper costs for clarity, comparability, transparency, reliability, reporting analysis; for companies - reducing the cost of raising capital, a single accounting system, no need to compare financial data, the consistency of internal and external accounting; for auditors - uniform accounting principles, the opportunity to participate in the adoption of standards, training on a global scale; for developers of national standards - exchange of experience, the basis for national standards, increasing confidence in national standards, convergence of standards; for developing countries - reducing the cost of developing national standards, attracting investors.

In conclusion, it should not be expected that foreign investment will come to Uzbekistan soon if Uzbekistan fully transfers to the IFRS. However, this will be an important step in strengthening mutual trust between Uzbekistan and the international community. Increasing corporate transparency means that investments will be less risky for investors and therefore cheaper. Obviously, no national financial market can develop normally without being separated from the international market.

The results of the reforms in recent years show that in addition to the problems of the transition period, there are some positive results. However, reform can only take place when every accountant has a professional knowledge of the basics of IFRS and when company executives are really interested in providing reliable and objective information. This means that we need to work harder to improve the skills of accountants.

It should be noted that the reform of accounting is not through a blind copy of the Western experience, but taking into account the established national traditions, the peculiarities of economic development of Uzbekistan. should be done. Therefore, inconsistencies need to be gradually mitigated at this stage of the accounting system reform.

However, when it comes to reform, it should be noted that the IFRS cannot be adopted automatically, without any changes. In fact, international standards serve as a compromise between the world's leading accounting systems.

Probably the main conclusion from the first results of the reform of the accounting system of Uzbekistan is the presence of certain positive results. It is extremely important that the reform continues at the pace it has achieved.

It is hoped that Uzbek companies will speak the same language as international business and will act as equal partners in foreign markets, which will allow them to take full advantage of the wide range of opportunities provided by international capital markets.

Thus, much remains to be done to ensure Russia's full transition to international accounting practices.

It is important that the need for transition be recognized both at the government level and in the business and accounting community.

References:

1. Baychurin U.X., The main problems of the transition to IFRS. Buxgalter tatarstana 2013-№16. 68-69 b.
2. Birin A.O, Ganina I.V., Evseyev V.M., The main problems of the transition to IFRS. International accountingi 2014. №3 4-8 b.
3. Qudbiyev, N. T. (2021). The urgency of the transition to International Financial Accounting Standards. Relevance of the transition to international financial accounting standards. SJ international journal of theoretical and practical research, 1(2), 56 -64.